

Integrating in vitro and in silico techniques for evaluating the antioxidant activity of *Chrysanthemum indicum* L

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Abstract

The prevalence of degenerative diseases has been escalating due to the mounting presence of oxidative stress conditions, characterized by elevated levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Oxidative stress triggers genetic alterations, structural modifications, and the progression of various degenerative disorders, including cancer, diabetes, Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, rheumatoid arthritis, and osteoporosis. Consequently, the modulation of redox homeostasis and attenuation of oxidative stress through the activity of antioxidant compounds play crucial roles. *Chrysanthemum indicum* L., an herb with rich historical usage for alleviating diverse discomforts and oxidative stress-related ailments, possesses potential antioxidant properties. Nevertheless, the precise mechanism underlying its efficacy remains poorly understood. In this study, the antioxidant potential of chrysanthemum flower ethanol extract was investigated by assessing its ability to inhibit 2,2-dyphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radicals. Additionally, the detected compounds present in chrysanthemum flowers were computationally docked to the key macromolecular receptors involved in reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, namely Cytochrome P450 (CP450) and NADPH oxidase (NO). The findings revealed that the ethanolic extract in chrysanthemum flowers displayed inhibitory activity against 2,2-dyphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radicals at a concentration of 1.35 µg/mL, which is comparable to that of vitamin C (0.7 µg/mL). Moreover, the bioactive compounds present in the ethanolic extract of chrysanthemum flowers, namely 3-hydroxyspirost-8-en-11-one, ingenol 3-hexadecanoate, and Ergosta-5,22-dien-3-ol acetate, were subjected to docking simulations with CP450 and NO receptors. The binding-free energies (BFEs) acquired for the compound 3-Hydroxyspirost-8-en-11-one were determined to be -12.7 kcal/mol and -12.4 kcal/mol for CP450 and NO receptors, respectively. Similarly, the compound Ingenol 3-hexadecanoate exhibited BFE values of -9.5 kcal/mol and -10.7 kcal/mol, while the compound Ergosta-5,22-dien-3-ol acetate displayed BFEs of -8.9 kcal/mol and -8.1 kcal/mol for CP450 and NO receptors, respectively. In contrast, the control substances 5-fluorouracil (FLU) and dextromethorphan (DEX) demonstrated BFEs of -4.9 kcal/mol and -6.5 kcal/mol, respectively, for each receptor. Collectively, our findings suggest that chrysanthemum extract holds promise as a natural antioxidant source for alleviating oxidative stress and preventing the progression of degenerative diseases, including cancer and diabetes.

Keywords

Chrysanthemum indicum L, antioxidant, ROS, in vitro, in silico

Introduction

Recent discoveries have identified certain diseases that arise due to the impact of reactive oxygen species (ROS), commonly referred to as free radicals. ROS are small oxygen-derived molecules that possess the ability to act as oxidizing agents or transform into oxygen radicals (André-Lévine et al. 2017). Elevated levels of ROS in the body have been linked to a variety of diseases, including cardiovascular, immune, nervous system, aging, and cancer disorders. According to a recent study, selectively targeting specific ROS levels enabled the development of futuristic subtle redox drugs. Elevated levels of ROS within the body have been associated with various diseases, including cardiovascular, immune, nervous system, aging, and cancer-related disorders. Recent research has shown that selectively targeting specific ROS levels has paved the way for the development of innovative redox drugs (Sammar et al. 2019; Sies and Jones 2020). Conditions such as diabetes, neurodegenerative diseases, cardiovascular diseases, and cancer can be triggered by heightened oxidative stress (White et al. 2014). This stress emerges from the activation of various transcription factors that can stimulate the expression of numerous genes, including growth factors and inflammatory cytokines. Consequently, these changes lead to the transformation of normal cells into cancerous cells by activating inflammatory pathways (Reuter et al. 2010). Therefore, the preservation of redox homeostasis and the mitigation of oxidative stress rely on the effective presence of antioxidants within cells, as they serve as the primary and secondary defense mechanisms after the antioxidant enzymes and proteolytic and lipolytic enzymes have been surpassed (Cadenas 1997). A number of enzymes, including cytochrome P450 (CP450), lipoxygenase (LO), myeloperoxidase (MP), NADPH oxidase (NO), and xanthine oxidase (XO), are recognized for their ability to generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) during the metabolism of arachidonic acid. By inhibiting these enzymes, the cycle of ROS production is disrupted, resulting in a subsequent decrease in oxidative stress and the preservation of redox homeostasis (Dharmaraja 2017). The development of certain diseases can be attributed to an initiation of oxidative stress mediated by reactive oxygen species (ROS). Consequently, the exploration for agents capable of preserving the equilibrium of redox homeostasis, particularly antioxidants, assumes a crucial role in the identification of molecules that possess the ability to hinder and impede the proliferation of cancer cells by diminishing oxidative stress (Cadenas 1997; Reuter et al. 2010; White et al. 2014; Dharmaraja 2017).

The utilization of herbal remedies is gaining global popularity, as it is widely acknowledged and disseminated as a secure dietary composition and supplement with antioxidant properties (Ekor 2014). *Chrysanthemum* is recognized as one of the top four globally renowned cut flowers. *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. has been traditionally used in various cultural practices, particularly in Asia, not only for ornamental purposes but also for

medicinal applications. In addition to their ornamental value, chrysanthemums have demonstrated promising medicinal properties (Yuan et al. 2020). Throughout Asia, chrysanthemum flowers and their extracts have been extensively employed for an extended period to alleviate a variety of discomfort symptoms. These applications include enhancing liver functionality as well as alleviating symptoms of redness and itchiness in the eyes (Jeong et al. 2013). Ethnobotanical studies emphasize the plant's multifaceted use, while ethnopharmacological research has identified its potential in exhibiting anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and hepatoprotective effects (Akinwunmi et al. 2021; Liu et al. 2022). These traditional applications have inspired modern scientific research into the plant's bioactive constituents, such as flavonoids and phenolic acids, known for their antioxidant properties. *Chrysanthemum* has demonstrated its ability to mitigate liver injury induced by acetaminophen in rats by inhibiting oxidative stress and apoptosis (Zhou et al. 2021). While numerous *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies have highlighted the antioxidant properties of chrysanthemums, and several potential antioxidant compounds such as caffeic acid, apigenin, luteolin, and glucosides have been identified, the underlying molecular mechanisms remain poorly understood (Chen et al. 2012). Existing literature suggests that molecular tethering has emerged as a valuable tool for investigating receptor-ligand interactions involved in the inhibition of enzymes associated with antioxidant activity. This technique has contributed to resolving uncertainties and providing insights into potential receptor regions implicated in the activity, identification of amino acid residues engaged in the interaction, and the specific atoms involved in direct ligand interactions (Gupta et al. 2018).

The assessment of molecular dynamics and ligand-receptor tethering in the context of molecular docking typically involves the comparison of root mean squared deviation (RMSD) values, which determine the positional variance between tethered ligands and naturally co-crystallized ligands within proteins (Sargsyan et al. 2017; Velázquez-Libera et al. 2020). In conjunction with molecular docking, the evaluation of potential drug candidates commonly entails an analysis of drug-likeness and their absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity (ADMET) profiles. Drug-likeness is generally assessed according to Lipinski's rule (also known as the rule of five or Ro5), while ADMET predictions provide insights into oral bioavailability, cellular permeability, metabolism, elimination, and toxicity—representing the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic characteristics of a drug compound (Kalita et al. 2019). Notably, the design of orally administered active drugs must adhere to Lipinski's R05, which outlines specific criteria. The pharmacokinetic profile serves as a fundamental basis for drug development, as the efficacy of a drug in eliciting a pharmacological effect largely depends on its pharmacokinetic parameters. Consequently, analyzing the pharmacokinetic profile is essential for enhancing compound effectiveness (Plescia and Moitessier 2020).

Cytochrome P450 (CYPs) enzymes play a pivotal role in both the formation and treatment of cancer. They are involved in the metabolic activation of numerous pro-carcinogens and participate in the inactivation and activation of anticancer drugs (Rodriguez-Antona and Ingelman-Sundberg 2006). Studies have demonstrated that the enzyme nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) oxidase, as the primary source of reactive oxygen species (ROS), contributes to the pathology of acute brain injuries and chronic neurodegenerative disorders (Bedard and Krause 2007; Gao et al. 2012). However, NADPH oxidase also plays a role in physiological processes within the brain (Lambeth and Neish 2014; Nayernia et al. 2014). Despite the known health benefits of *Chrysanthemum indicum*, limited studies have comprehensively elucidated the underlying antioxidant mechanisms at a molecular level. Addressing these gaps is crucial to unlocking the full potential of *Chrysanthemum indicum* as a preventive treatment for oxidative stress-related diseases, such as cancer and diabetes, which continue to pose major global health challenges.

The aim of this study was to investigate the antioxidant potential of chrysanthemum flower ethanolic extract in vitro, specifically through DPPH radical inhibition, in comparison to ascorbic acid. Additionally, the study aimed to explore the antioxidant properties of bioactive compounds derived from chrysanthemum flower extract (*Chrysanthemum indicum* L.) using in silico molecular docking with two enzymes, namely cytochrome P450-CP450 and NADPH oxidase-NO. These antioxidant properties were compared against known molecules acting as positive controls, namely 5-fluorouracil (FLU) for cytochrome P450-CP450 and dextromethorphan (DEX) for NADPH oxidase-NO. Furthermore, the study included a pharmacokinetic analysis based on Lipinski's Rule of Five (Ro5) criteria. This research addresses a significant gap in understanding the precise molecular mechanisms of *Chrysanthemum indicum* L.'s antioxidant properties, which remain underexplored despite its extensive traditional use. By combining in vitro and in silico approaches, this study not only provides new insights into how specific bioactive compounds interact with key ROS-related enzymes but also contributes novel data that can enhance the development of natural antioxidant therapies.

Material and methods

Antioxidant in vitro analysis of *Chrysanthemum indicum* L. ethanolic extract

Preparation of analytical solutions

A stock solution of 1000 µg/mL was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of *Chrysanthemum indicum* ethanolic extract in 100 mL of ethanol in a measuring flask. Subsequently, various concentrations (2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 µg/mL) were prepared by diluting 5 mL of the stock solution. For

each concentration, 1 mL of the extract was mixed with 2 mL of DPPH solution in a test tube. The solution was vortexed for 5 seconds and incubated at room temperature for 30 minutes. The absorbance of each solution was then measured.

The choice to use ethanol as a solvent for the extraction in the DPPH bioactivity test is based on its ability to dissolve a wide range of bioactive compounds, including polyphenols, flavonoids, and terpenoids, which are commonly associated with antioxidant activity. Ethanol is also relatively safe, easy to handle, and effective in extracting both polar and moderately non-polar compounds, making it a preferred solvent in antioxidant studies.

Antioxidant activity test using the DPPH method

The IC₅₀ value, which indicates the concentration at which a 50% reduction in DPPH activity is observed, was utilized to evaluate the outcomes of the antioxidant activity experiment conducted using the DPPH method. The instrument used to measure the outcomes of the DPPH radical scavenging activity was a UV-visible spectrophotometer. The absorbance of the samples was recorded at a wavelength of 517 nm, which is the standard wavelength for monitoring the decrease in DPPH absorbance. The IC₅₀ value for the extract was determined by analyzing the provided solutions. A control solution containing 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) at a concentration of 0.1 mM was employed. The radical scavenging activity was measured as the percentage inhibition and calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{DPPH Scavenging Activity (\%)} = (A_0 - A_1) / A_0 \times 100$$

The variable denoted as A₀ represents the absorbance value observed in the control group, while the variable A₁ denotes the absorbance value recorded in the experimental samples (Tallei et al. 2023).

Subsequently, the acquired results were visually depicted through a linear regression plot. In this plot, the concentration values were assigned to the x-axis, while the percent inhibition values were assigned to the y-axis. By utilizing this linear regression equation, the IC₅₀ value for each sample was determined. The IC₅₀ value is represented by a y-coordinate of 50 and an x-coordinate corresponding to the IC₅₀ (Molyneux 2004). The antioxidant activity of a compound is classified as very strong if its IC₅₀ is less than 50 µg/mL, strong if it falls within the range of 50–100 µg/mL, moderate if it lies between 100–150 µg/mL, and weak if it ranges from 151–200 µg/mL (Blois 1958).

Antioxidant activity test using the ABTS method

Measurement of antioxidant activity was carried out by first making a stock solution of 100 µg/mL extract. Pipetted 1 mL, 2 mL, 3 mL, 4 mL, and 5 mL and added 1 mL of ABTS solution and then sufficient with ethanol up to 10 mL so that a solution with concentrations of 10 ppm,

20 ppm, 30 ppm, 40 ppm, and 50 ppm was obtained. Homogenized and measured on UV-Vis spectrophotometry at a wavelength of 750 nm. Sample measurements were carried out three times (triplo). Inhibition activity is calculated using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{\text{Blank Absorbance} - \text{Sample Absorbance}}{\text{Blank Absorbance}} \times 100\%$$

Antioxidant activity test using the FRAP method

A stock solution of 100 µg/mL was made by taking 10 mg of sample dissolved in 100 mL of ethanol. The stock solution is made into series solutions of 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 µg/mL by pipetting 1 mL, 2 mL, 3 mL, 4 mL, and 5 mL, respectively, and sufficient with ethanol up to 10 mL. After that, take 1 mL from each concentration into the test tube, add 1 mL of solution with pH 6.6 phosphate and 1 mL of 1% $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ solution, and then incubate. Next, 1 mL of trichloroacetate (TCA) was added and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes, then pipetted 1 mL of supernatant, 1 mL of aquades, and 0.5 ml of 0.1% $FeCl_3$. The solution is left for 10 minutes by first homogenizing. Absorbance is measured at a wavelength of 720 nm. Measurements were carried out three times (triplo).

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{\text{Blank Absorbance}}{\text{Ascorbic Absorbance}}\right) \times 100\%$$

Molecular docking analysis of bioactive compounds of chrysanthemum flower

Bioactive compounds of *Chrysanthemum* extracts were identified using the gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) performed at the Integrated Research and Testing Laboratory of Gadjah Mada University (LPPT UGM) (Jelita et al. 2019; Teoh et al. 2023). Molecular docking was performed using YASARA-Structure 22.8.22, and the receptor preparation was conducted using BIOVIA Discovery Studio. The ligand structures obtained from GCMS analysis were sourced from PubChem (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>), while the receptors were acquired from RCSB PDB (<https://www.rcsb.org/pdb/>).

Ligand and receptor preparation

The structures of Cytochrome P450 (CP450) and NADPH oxidase (NO) were obtained in .pdb format. YASARA structure software was utilized to isolate proteins from solvents, ligands, and nonstandard residues, involving the removal of water molecules, addition of hydrogen atoms, and elimination of unnecessary chains. Default parameters were applied for other settings (Wang et al. 2019).

Molecular docking validation

The docking method was validated by analyzing the conformation of the original ligand. The obtained docking results were compared with the conformation of the original

crystallographic ligand, serving as a reference for inhibitor validation and standardization (Gonzalez et al. 2019). Grid box settings for the docking process were determined based on the ligand-bound space observed in protein macromolecules during download. The validation utilized the YASARA structure application with the dock_run.mcr macro and run=25 parameter, employing the Amber03 force field (Patel et al. 2021). The grid box was adjusted to a positional distance of 5 Å from the native ligand of each receptor. Subsequently, a docking process using a virtual screening approach was conducted using the macros provided in the default YASARA file. Redocking was performed to identify the optimal grid box size, which was then employed for screening purposes. The dock_run-screening YASARA macro file structure was utilized to attach an unlimited number of ligands to the target receptors using the AutoDock Vina method (http://www.yasara.org/dock_runscreening.mcr). The screening was performed using the YASARA Structure with the dock_runscreening.mcr macro, with the run parameter set to 25 and employing the Amber03 method (Patel et al. 2021).

Molecular docking between the receptor and target ligands

The YASARA application was employed for the molecular docking process, with separate optimization of macromolecules and ligands. The resulting structures were saved in the same folder. Docking was performed using a grid box, and energy minimization parameters were adjusted based on validation results. To enable efficient docking, the .smi format file was converted to .sdf format using the smi2sdf.mcr macro, creating a combined format containing ligand data in SMILES-based representation. The resulting file underwent docking using a virtual screening approach, utilizing macros from the default YASARA file for the validated virtual target. AutoDock Vina was employed as the docking algorithm in YASARA Structure to search for dock poses, and the AMBER03 force field was used to score receptor-ligand interactions (Patel et al. 2019).

The docking calculation results were examined in the output format displayed in Notepad. The determination of the ligand conformation was based on selecting the pose with the lowest BFE, indicating the most favorable binding. To visualize the interactions between the ligand and receptor, Biovia Discovery Studio Visualizer 2020 was utilized. The complexes were ranked according to their highest binding affinity, which was represented by the lowest BFE value.

ADMET predictions

The ADMET properties of compounds, including Lipinski's Rule of Five (Ro5), gastrointestinal (GI) absorption, permeability across the blood-brain barrier (BBB), and cytochrome inhibition, were calculated using the SwissADME web server (Lipinski 2004; Daina et al. 2017; Karim et al. 2019). The SMILES format of each compound was submitted to the server to obtain the relevant predictions.

Results and discussion

Antioxidant value of *Chrysanthemum* flower extract

Antioxidant activity test using the DPPH method

The results of the DPPH radical inhibition assay conducted on the chrysanthemum flower extract, along with ascorbic acid as a control, are depicted in Tables 1, 2. DPPH is a stable organic free radical that undergoes a loss in its absorption spectrum at 515–528 nm upon electron acceptance (Chithiraikumar et al. 2017). The antioxidant potential of the extract, evaluated using the DPPH assay, is quantified by the percentage of inhibitory value. The findings revealed that both the extract and ascorbic acid exhibited a linear increase in percent inhibition as the concentration increased. This indicates that higher concentrations of antioxidants in the extract confer greater effectiveness against free radicals.

The results of the DPPH radical inhibition assay revealed that the chrysanthemum flower extract exhibited a comparable level of activity to ascorbic acid, a well-known antioxidant compound. This suggests that the extract possesses a high potential as an effective antioxidant in inhibiting DPPH free radicals. The DPPH assay is widely recognized for its simplicity, accuracy, and frequent use in assessing the free radical scavenging ability of various plant extracts (Dudonné et al. 2009). The IC_{50} values, calculated for the ascorbic acid extract, provide quantitative information on its antioxidant activity and can be found in Tables 1, 2, and Fig. 1. These values represent the concentration of the extract needed to reduce DPPH free radicals by 50%. Therefore, a lower IC_{50} value indicates a higher antioxidant activity of the extract, as it requires a lower concentration to achieve the desired level of radical inhibition (Fatimawali et al. 2023). Upon interaction with the chrysanthemum

Figure 1. The results of the DPPH radical inhibition assay performed on the chrysanthemum flower extract (2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 µg/mL), with ascorbic acid serving as the control.

flower extract, the DPPH solution undergoes a visible color change from purple to yellow. This color transformation occurs due to the reduction of DPPH radicals, as the extract donates electrons or hydrogen atoms to neutralize the radicals, thereby converting them into non-radical compounds (Munteanu and Apetrei 2021). This change in color confirms the antioxidant activity of the chrysanthemum flower extract in effectively neutralizing DPPH free radicals. The results underscore the significant antioxidant capacity of the chrysanthemum flower extract, positioning it as a prospective and valuable natural resource for bioactive compounds possessing potent free radical scavenging properties.

Antioxidant activity test using the ABTS method

The principle of testing antioxidant activity with the ABTS method is the removal of ABTS cation color to measure the capacity of antioxidants that directly react with ABTS cation radicals. ABTS is a radical with a nitrogen center that has a characteristic blue-green color, which when reduced by antioxidants will change to a non-radical form from colored to colorless.

Table 1. The calculated IC_{50} values for the Chrysanthemum extract.

Concentration (µg/mL)	Absorbance (A)			Average	% Inhibition	IC_{50} (µg/mL)
	A1	A2	A3			
10	0.109	0.098	0.098	0.101	87.900	1.35
8	0.158	0.147	0.146	0.150	82.053	
6	0.226	0.211	0.211	0.216	74.240	
4	0.248	0.289	0.289	0.275	67.164	
2	0.343	0.345	0.344	0.344	58.934	
Control DPPH	0.838	0.837	0.839	0.838	–	

Table 2. The calculated IC_{50} values for ascorbic acid.

Concentration (µg/mL)	Absorbance (A)			Average	% Inhibition	IC_{50} (µg/mL)
	A1	A2	A3			
2.5	0.224	0.226	0.223	0.224	73.230	0.71
2	0.254	0.247	0.249	0.250	70.151	
1.5	0.345	0.349	0.299	0.331	60.505	
1	0.381	0.376	0.376	0.378	54.940	
0.5	0.449	0.468	0.468	0.461	44.960	
Control DPPH	0.838	0.839	0.837	0.838	–	

Table 3 shows the results of antioxidant activity testing with the ABTS method. Based on the results of the antioxidant activity test carried out, *Chrysanthemum* ethanol extract has an IC_{50} value of 10.4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Antioxidant activity test using the FRAP method

In principle, the determination of antioxidant activity using the FRAP method can run well if it is carried out on antioxidant compounds that can reduce ferri-tri-*pyridyl*-triazine (Fe(III)TPTZ) to ferro-tri-*pyridyl*-triazine (Fe(II)TPTZ) complexes. Measurements were made three times at a wavelength of 720 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The absorbed value obtained is used to find the % reducing power value. Creating a curve where x is the concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) of y as % reducing power, then the linear regression equation $y = ax + b$ is obtained.

Table 4 shows the results of antioxidant activity testing with the FRAP method. Based on the results of the antioxidant activity test conducted by ethanol extract, yellow *chrysanthemum* has an IC_{50} value of 26.7 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

The extract derived from *chrysanthemum* flowers exhibits a remarkably low IC_{50} value comparable to that of ascorbic acid, indicating its potent antioxidant activity (Jun et al. 2003; Molyneux 2004). Ascorbic acid, a synthetic antioxidant, effectively mitigates the presence of free radicals, including hydroxyl and peroxy intermediates, thereby reducing lipid peroxidation in cellular membranes. Antioxidants, whether natural or synthetic, play a crucial role in minimizing the risk of various diseases by preventing oxidative damage inflicted upon biological systems, encompassing cells, tissues, and macromolecules. This damage arises from reactive oxygen species (ROS) and is associated with liver ailments, neurodegenerative disorders, cancer, and degenerative conditions, as well as chronic diseases (Lobo et al. 2010; Nimse and Pal 2015; Gao et al. 2016). Consequently, the robust antioxidant properties demonstrated by *chrysanthemum* flowers present a promising avenue for addressing health issues associated with oxidative stress. Substantiating this, a previous study highlighted the pronounced antioxidant activity of purple *chrysanthemum* tea in comparison to

its yellow counterpart, as evidenced by the results of the DPPH radical scavenging assay. This outcome aligns with the elevated presence of anthocyanins, which are widely acknowledged for their potent antioxidant attributes, within the purple *chrysanthemum* tea (Han et al. 2019). Several studies also indicated that *chrysanthemum* flowers, which are rich in flavonoids and phenolic acids, exhibit potent antioxidant activity (Han et al. 2017; Kim et al. 2022; Tumilaar et al. 2024).

Molecular docking between CP450 and NO receptors with bioactive compounds of *Chrysanthemum* flower

Molecular docking validation

The docking analysis involves parameters such as root-mean square deviation (RMSD) to measure the error deviation during docking. Valid docking methods have $RMSD \leq 2 \text{ \AA}$ (Muttuqaqin et al. 2019). Energy minimization stabilizes protein-protein bonds, and the docking procedure is iterated up to 10 times to achieve the smallest RMSD (Rachmania 2019). A smaller RMSD value signifies a lower degree of error deviation during the docking process.

The validation process redocks the original ligand optimized with VegaZZ, aiming to assess docking characteristics and correlation with X-ray crystallography data. The molecular docking process yielded crystallographic poses with significant overlap (represented by the cyan-colored orientation and conformation). These poses were accompanied by low RMSD values, indicating favorable results (Fig. 2). These results demonstrate the effectiveness of the applied protocol in analyzing molecular interactions between receptors and ligands.

The redocking process began using VegaZZ software to optimize the original ligand, ensuring that the ligand structure was prepared correctly for docking. The optimized ligand was then redocked into the active site of the target protein using the same molecular docking software and parameters employed in the primary docking experiments. The purpose of this redocking step was to evaluate the root-mean-square deviation

Table 3. Antioxidant activity of white *chrysanthemum* (*Chrysanthemum indicum* L.) ABTS method analysis results.

Sample	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Inhibition Activity (% Inhibition)	IC_{50} ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
Chrysanthemum Extract	10	48.65	10,4
	20	55.39	
	30	60.81	
	40	64.36	
	50	68.54	

Table 4. Antioxidant activity of white *chrysanthemum* (*Chrysanthemum indicum* L.) results of FRAP method analysis.

Sample	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Inhibition Activity (% Inhibition)	IC_{50} ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
Chrysanthemum Extract	10	33.80	26.7
	20	41.76	
	30	52.49	
	40	64.59	
	50	74.91	

Figure 2. Superimposition of poses between the native ligands during the validation procedure. **A.** Cytochrome P450 CYP2C9 (PDB ID: 1OG5) with its native ligand S-warfarin (RMSD 0.7120 Å); **B.** NAD(P)H Oxidase (PDB ID: 2CDU) with its native ligand adenosine-5-diphosphat (ADP) (RMSD 0.8095 Å).

(RMSD) between the redocked ligand and the ligand's position as determined by X-ray crystallography. An RMSD value of less than 2.0 Å is generally considered acceptable, indicating that the docking method accurately reproduces the experimentally determined binding pose. This comparison between the computationally derived and experimentally observed ligand conformations provides a measure of the docking method's reliability. Additionally, the redocking results were analyzed for key interactions, such as hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic contacts, and π - π stacking, to ensure that the docking model replicates critical binding features observed in the crystal structure.

Molecular docking results

Molecular docking constitutes a dependable approach for the identification of novel drugs and drug compounds. By predicting the binding interactions between intricate compounds, referred to as ligands, and target proteins, valuable insights can be gained regarding the potential of these compounds as viable drug candidates capable of inhibiting specific pathological processes (Ganten et al. 2006; Alnoman et al. 2020). The molecular docking study was conducted to investigate the interaction between the CP450 receptor and NO with ligands derived from bioactive compounds extracted from chrysanthemum flowers. The criteria for selecting ligands for molecular docking included factors such as molecular weight, solubility, and the presence of functional groups known to influence antioxidant activity. Additionally, compounds with significant pharmacokinetic properties, such as bioavailability and binding affinity to target proteins, were prioritized. The specific phytochemicals docked—such as ingenol 3-hexadecanoate, 3-hydroxyspirost-8-en-11-one, and ergosta-5,22-dien-3-ol, acetate—were chosen due to their presence in *Chrysanthemum indicum* and their documented bioactive roles in combating oxidative stress. These compounds have been reported to exhibit strong antioxidant properties, justifying their inclusion in the study to understand their potential interactions and efficacy in inhibiting oxidative pathways (Kalogeropoulos et al. 2013; Iftikhar et al. 2019). The results of the docking analysis are presented in Table 5.

Cytochrome P450 enzymes (CYPs) play crucial roles in both the development of cancer and its treatment. These enzymes are involved in the metabolic activation of numerous procarcinogens and also participate in the inactivation and activation processes of anticancer drugs (Rodríguez-Antona and Ingelman-Sundberg 2006). Found predominantly in the smooth endoplasmic reticulum of hepatocytes and epithelial cells of the small intestine, cytochrome P450 (CYP450) constitutes a group of enzymes. Their primary function involves the oxidative catalysis of various endogenous and exogenous substances. CYP450 enzymes are extensively involved in the phase I metabolism of approximately 80% of currently utilized drugs, including anticancer agents. Moreover, they contribute to the synthesis of diverse hormones and exert influences on hormone-related cancers (Mittal et al. 2015).

In this research, a total of 25 bioactive compounds obtained from the extract of chrysanthemum flowers were investigated as ligands, while the target proteins used were CYP450 and NO receptors. Table 3 presents the results indicating that three out of the twenty-five ligands exhibited significantly low binding energies when interacting with the receptors. Conversely, the remaining molecules tested displayed negligible binding energies, rendering them unsuitable for further analysis. The assessment of binding energies is a crucial parameter in evaluating the strength of molecular interactions between ligands and receptors (Tallei et al. 2021a). A lower or more negative BFE value signifies a stronger and more effective interaction between the ligand and receptor. Among the ligands examined, 3-hydroxyspirost-8-en-11-one exhibited the lowest BFE values for both receptors, with BFE values of -12.7 and -12.4 kcal/mol. The ligand 3-palmitate Ingenol ranked second with BFE of -9.5 and -10.7 kcal/mol, followed by Ergosta-5,22-dien-3-ol, acetate, (3 β ,22E)- as the third lowest with BFE of -8.9 and -8.1 kcal/mol. Notably, these values were lower than the control compounds, FLU, which exhibited a BFE value of -4.5 kcal/mol for the CYP450 receptor, and DEX, with a BFE value of -6.9 kcal/mol for the NO receptor. The ligand with the lowest binding energy indicates the formation of the strongest complex with the highest receptor affinity when compared to other bioactive compounds.

Table 5. Results of molecular docking analyses conducted on bioactive compounds derived from *Chrysanthemum* flower extract.

PubChem ID	Molecular Formula	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	IUPAC Name of the Compounds	Binding-free Energy (Kcal/mol)	
				CP450	NO
628694	C ₂₇ H ₄₀ O ₄	428	3-Hydroxyspirost-8-en-11-one	-12.7	-12.4
622252	C ₃₆ H ₅₈ O ₆	586	Ingenol 3- palmitate	-9.5	-10.7
6432458	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O ₂	440	Ergosta-5,22-dien-3-ol, acetate, (3β,22E)-	-8.9	-8.1
6452096	C ₂₆ H ₄₄ O ₅	436	Ethyl iso-allocholate	-8.6	-6.8
5363101	C ₂₃ H ₃₂ O	324	2-[4-methyl-6-(2,6,6-trimethylcyclohex-1-enyl) hexa-1,3,5-trienyl] cyclohex-1-en-1-carboxaldehyde	-8.3	-7.9
91354	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204	Alloaromadendrene	-8.1	-6.1
91753574	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	220	cis-Z-alpha-Bisabolene epoxide	-7.8	-6.5
21160048	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ O ₄	444	9-Octadecenoic acid, (2-phenyl-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl) methyl ester, cis-	-7.7	-6.9
25203064	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204	β-Longipinene	-7.6	6.6
521207	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204	Cedrene	-7.6	-6.2
1742210	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	220	Caryophyllene oxide	-7.6	-6.1
21262075	C ₁₆ H ₃₂	224	1-Nonylcycloheptane	-6.6	-6.0
91692753	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₂	214	(Z)-2-(Hepta-2,4-diyne-1-ylidene)-1,6-dioxaspiro [4.4] non-3-ene	-6.5	-6.1
292285	C ₂₆ H ₅₄	366	Octadecane, 3-ethyl-5-(2-ethylbutyl)-	-6.3	-5.4
183823	C ₉ H ₁₂ FNO ₂	185	Benzeneethanamine, 2-fluoro-beta,5-dihydroxy-N-methyl-	-6.2	-5.9
5365022	C ₃₅ H ₇₀	490	17-Pentatriacontene	-6.2	-5.7
537071	C ₃₇ H ₇₆ O	536	1-Heptatriacotanol	-6.2	-5.5
538453	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ O ₂	290	12,15-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester	-5.9	-5.9
99931	C ₃₅ H ₆₈ O ₅	568	Hexadecanoic acid, 1-(hydroxymethyl)-1,2-ethanediyl ester	-5.8	-6.5
75050	C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O ₂	314	Ethanol, 2-(octadecyloxy)-	-5.8	-5.2
21159937	C ₃₈ H ₇₆ O ₃	592	Oleic acid, 3-(octadecyloxy)propyl ester	-5.8	-5.7
8222	C ₂₀ H ₄₂	282	Eicosane	-5.8	-4.7
545593	C ₂₇ H ₅₅ Cl	414	Heptacosane, 1-chloro-	-5.7	-5.7
11636	C ₂₇ H ₅₆	380	Heptacosane	-5.7	-5.4
5366411	C ₄₂ H ₆₄ O ₂	600	.psi.psi.-Carotene, 1,1',2,2'-tetrahydro-1,1'-dimethoxy-	1.7	-7.7
Control 1			5-fluorouracil (FLU)	-4.9	-
Control 2			Dextromethorphan (DEX)	-	-6.5
Cocrystal ligands			S-warfarin (SWF)	-10.5	-
			Adenocine-5-diphosphat (ADP)	-	-8.7

Visualization results of molecular docking

Fig. 3 illustrates the visual representation of the molecular docking results, specifically showcasing the binding of the three ligands to the CYP450. Additionally, Fig. 4 depicts the binding of the ligands to the NO receptor. The interactions between the ligands and the amino acids constituting the CYP450 and NO enzymes involve the formation of various types of bonds. Notably, hydrogen bonds (H-bonds) are covalent bonds that occur between hydrogen atoms in electronegative donors and free electron pairs from other highly electronegative atoms. These H-bonds play a pivotal role in determining the structure, function, and conformational dynamics of biological systems (Herschlag and Pinney 2018; Tallei et al. 2020, 2021b). The findings of this study demonstrate the presence of H-bonds in the receptor-ligand complexes, as depicted in Figs 3, 4, and Table 6. H-bonds formed between proteins and ligands are specific and serve as crucial components of molecular recognition. These bonds represent a significant class of molecular interactions in biological systems, and their presence enhances the structural integrity and stability of the complexes (Hubbard and Kamran Haider 2010; Tallei et al. 2021b).

The strength of a bond and the stability of the energy score are influenced by the number of hydrogen bonds formed with amino acid residues (Shah R and Misra 2011). Hydrophobic interactions between ligands and receptors can reduce the interaction between amino acid residues and wa-

ter molecules. These hydrophobic interactions can take the form of pi-sigma and alkyl/pi-alkyl bonds [55]. Nonpolar (hydrophobic) amino acid residues tend to cluster together within the protein's interior, preventing or minimizing contact with water molecules (Arwansyah et al. 2014).

Referring to Table 4, it can be observed that only ingenol 3-palmitate forms salt bridges, particularly with ASP residues (A:179). Salt bridges commonly arise through interactions involving aspartic acid residues (Celik et al. 2022). On the other hand, van der Waals interactions are relatively weak electric attractions that result from permanent or induced molecular polarity (Widiastuti 2019). Although not as strong as H-bonds, van der Waals interactions contribute significantly to the inhibitory effect of ligands on the intended receptor, owing to their considerable occurrence (Tallei et al. 2020).

Lipinski's Ro5 results

The pharmaceutical industry necessitates accurate drug similarity prediction to enhance the activity and effectiveness of compounds while minimizing the likelihood of selecting incorrect drug candidates (Roy et al. 2020). Table 7 presents the results of the analysis based on Lipinski's Ro5 for the evaluation of bioactive compounds derived from chrysanthemum flower extract used as ligands for target proteins. The parameters considered for assessing the drug-likeness of these bioactive compounds include molec-

Figure 3. The two-dimensional configuration of the molecular docking outcomes depicting the interaction between CP450 and the top-selected ligands, along with the control compounds.

Figure 4. The two-dimensional configuration of the molecular docking outcomes depicting the interaction between NO and the top-selected ligands, along with the control compounds.

Table 6. Interacting residues formation of the three best ligands against CP450 and NO receptor.

Receptors	Compounds	Interacting Amino Acids in the Receptors
CP450	Ingenol 3- palmitate	Conventional H-bonds: ASN(A:474), LEU(A:208) Van der Waals: ALA (A:103), ASN(A:217), SER(A:209), GLY(A:475), GLN(A:214), ILE(A:213), LEU(A:366) Pi-Pi: PHE (A:476), PHE (A:100); Pi-Alkyl: PRO (A:367), ALA(A:477), LEU(A:362)
	3-Hydroxyspirost-8-en-11-one	Conventional H-bonds: THR(A:364) Van der Waals: PHE (A:100), ALA(A:103) LEU(A:102), ALA(A:106), PHE(A:114), LEU(A:208), LEU(A:233), ASN(A:217), THR(A:364), LEU(A:388), LEU(A:366), PRO(A:367), SER(A:365), PHE(A:476)
	Ergosta-5,22-dien-3-ol, acetate, (3 β ,22E)-	Van der Waals: ARG(A:97), ILE(A:2015), LEU(A:2018), SER(A:209), GLN(A:214), ASN(A:217), LEU(A:366), LEU(A:388), VAL(A:479) Pi-Sigma: PHE(A:100), PHE(A:476); Alkyl: ALA(A:103), ALA(A:477); Pi-Alkyl: PRO(A:367)
	5-fluorouracil (FLU)	Conventional H-bonds: THR(A:364), SER(A:365) Van der Waals: PHE(A:100), LEU(A:366), LEU(A:388); Pi-Pi: PHE(A:476); Pi-Alkyl: PRO(A:367)
	S-Warfarin (SWF)	Conventional H-bonds: NALA(A:103); Carbon-Hydrogen Bond: ILE(A:99) Van der Waals: GLY(A:98), ILE(A:99), LEU(A:102), PHE(A:100), LEU(A:208), GLN(A:214), ILE(A:213), ASN(A:217), VAL(A:113), THR(A:364), SER(A:365), LEU(A:388) Pi-Pi: PHE(A:114), PHE(A:476) Pi-Alkyl: PRO(A:367), LEU(A:366)
NO	Ingenol 3- palmitate	Conventional H-bonds: GLY(A:156), GLY(A:180) Van der Waals: ILE(A:122), ILE(A:155), SER(A:157), GLY(A:158), TYR(A:159), ILE(A:178), HIS(A:181), TYR(A:188), VAL(A:214) Salt Bridge: ASP(A:179) Attractive charge: ASP(A:179) Carbon H-bond: ILE(A:243) Unfavorable positive-positive: LYS(A:187), LYS(A:213) Alkyl: ILE(A:160) Pi-Alkyl: PHE(A:245)
	3-Hydroxyspirost-8-en-11-one	Conventional H-bond: VAL(A:214) Van der Waals: ILE(A:122), ILE(A:155), GLY(A:156), SER(A:157), GLY(A:158), GLY(A:180), TYR(A:188) Attractive charge: ASP(A:179) Unfavorable positive-positive LYS(A:187); Pi-Alkyl: LYS(A:213), ILE(A:243)
	Ergosta-5,22-dien-3-ol, acetate, (3 β ,22E)-	Van der Waals: GLY(A:156), GLY(A:158), TYR(A:159), ASP(A:179), GLY(A:180), HIS(A:181), LYS(A:187), TYR(A:188), LYS(A:213), CYS(A:242), GLY(A:244), LEU(A:299) Alkyl: ILE(A:160) Pi-Alkyl: PHE(A:245), PRO(A:298), ILE(A:243)
	Dextromethorphan (DEX)	Van der Waals: CSX(A:42), GLY(A:158), ILE(A:243), GLY(A:244), PHE(A:245), ILE(A:297), SER(A:328) Pi-Alkyl: TYR(A:159), ILE(A:160), TYR(A:188), PRO(A:298) Alkyl: LEU(A:299)
	Adenosine-5-diphosphate (ADP)	Conventional H-bonds: ILE(A:160), TYR(A:188), GLY(A:180), VAL(A:214) Van der Waals: PRO(A:120), ILE(A:122), ILE(A:155), GLY(A:156), SER(A:157), TYR(A:159), GLY(A:161), ILE(A:178), HIS(A:181), GLY(A:244), PHE(A:245) Carbon H-bonds: GLY(A:158), ASP(A:179), CYS(A:242), ILE(A:243) Attractive charge: LYS(A:213) Unfavorable Acceptor-acceptor: CYS(A:242) Pi-cation: LYS(A:187)

Table 7. The results of Lipinski's Ro5 for the ligands exhibiting the most favorable BFE with their respective receptors.

Ro5 parameters	Ligands		
	Ingenol 3-hexadecanoate	3-Hydroxyspirost-8-en-11-one	Ergosta-5,22-dien-3-ol, acetate, (3 β ,22E)-
Molecular Weight < 500 D	312	428	398
H-Donor < 5	5	1	1
H-Acceptor < 10	6	4	1
Log P < 5	-0.053101	6.070132	7.235324
Molar Refraction 40–130	77,145782	134,81427	142,394775

ular weight, the number of hydrogen bond acceptors, the number of hydrogen bond donors, log P value, and molar refractivity (Kurnia et al. 2023). Potential drug candidates are expected to meet at least one of the following criteria: (1) molecular weight less than 500 daltons, (2) fewer than ten hydrogen bond acceptors, (3) fewer than five hydrogen bond donors, (4) log P value less than five, and (5) molar refractivity ranging between 40 and 130 (Ponnulakshmi et al. 2020; Tumilaar et al. 2020; Niode et al. 2021).

Among the ligands, Ingenol 3-hexadecanoate satisfies all the criteria of Lipinski's Rule of Five, indicating its potential suitability as an oral drug. However, both 3-Hydroxy Spirost-8-en-11-one and Ergosta-5,22-dien-3-ol, acetate, (3 β ,22E)- demonstrate two deviations from the Lipinski's Rule of Five criteria. Thus, further development efforts are necessary to consider these ligands as potential candidates for oral drug use. While Lipinski's Ro5 suggests that a compound should ideally have no more than one violation of the five criteria for optimal oral bioavailability, however, it only serves as a guideline rather than an absolute rule in determining a compound's suitability as a drug. In certain cases, compounds with more than one violation may still exhibit favorable pharmacokinetic properties and can be further optimized or investigated for potential drug development. The acceptability of such violations depends on several factors, including the specific target, therapeutic area, and overall drug development strategy.

Conclusion

Chrysanthemum flowers have been demonstrated to possess antioxidant activity both in vitro and in silico, making them potential agents for preventing degenerative diseases such as cancer and diabetes. In vitro assessment of the antioxidant activity of chrysanthemum flower extract yielded an IC₅₀ value of 1.3 μ g/mL. Comparatively, the synthetic compound ascorbic acid, used as a control, exhibited an IC₅₀ value of 0.7 μ g/mL. The chrysanthemum flower extract falls within the category of "very strong" antioxidant activity due to its IC₅₀ value being less than 50 μ g/mL. Noteworthy bioactive compounds responsible for the antioxidant activity of chrysanthemum flowers include ingenol 3-hexadecanoate, 3-hydroxy spirost-8-en-11-one, and ergosta-5,22-dien-3-ol, acetate, (3 β ,22E)-. Our findings indicate that chrysanthemum flowers not only exhibit very strong antioxidant activity but also demonstrate the potential for interaction with key enzymes involved in oxidative stress, such as Cytochrome P450 and NADPH oxidase. These results highlight the flower's prom-

ise as a natural therapeutic agent for mitigating oxidative stress and preventing degenerative diseases, warranting further investigation into its bioactive compounds and mechanisms of action.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Figure visualization of the chemical structure of *Chrysanthemum indicum* L.

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Data type: docx

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